

Textbook: Focus on Students' National Identity

Strategies for Shaping Student's National and Cultural Identity in Teaching "Cross-Cultural Theory Introduction"

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Abstract

This paper explains the didactic domain concept formed within the strategic matrix of the educational discourse related to teaching cross-cultural communication theory. It is stated that intercultural communication competences improved on certain strategies taking into account the organization of training in the light of the cognitive opposition "friend or other", acquiring a cross-cultural reflexive way of interaction, and further focus on value attitudes and participants' dominance in the communication act.

The authors share their experience of writing the manual which corresponds to the effective teaching techniques. The manual typically based on understanding national and cultural symbols in innovative polyphonic and polycode format, ingrained in media network, opts for analytical review and more precise study of theoretical methodology. The competency-based approach focuses on instrumental pragmatic approach to cross-cultural communication that is challenging, dialogic and creative. The article provides value- and practice-oriented outlook on the key strategies featured in the manual: assimilating information strategy (informative strategy); comparing two or more cultures reflexive strategy; valorization of native and foreign cultures strategy.

Keywords: didactic domain, manual, cultural identity, teaching strategies.

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Published by Moscow City University and peer-reviewed under responsibility of TSNI-2021 (Textbook: Focus on Students' National Identity)

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Introduction

The accelerated interest towards educational discourse as a prospective linguistic analysis object stems from the notion that discourse sets a certain matrix of verbal interaction (Discourse as universal matrix of social interaction, 2018). This discourse is a mixture of different genres with teaching foreign languages manuals on the top of scale. The manuals rely on such communicative and pragmatic categories as dialogism, address and strategy (Vikulova et al., 2020). Language codes as forms of transmitting social practice in system of education as well as core teaching strategies play a crucial role for educators.

The course *Introduction to the theory of cross-cultural communication*, both theoretically and primarily practically oriented, offers key categories rooted in cultural anthropology, psychology, cognitive and communicative functional insights of a value nature. Among the categories we will relate the effective interaction of language individuals – enophones – to such concepts as:

- tolerance, awareness to empathy;
- strong emphasis on overcoming egocentricity;
- avoiding social stereotypes and attribution mistakes in the prism of social and cultural identity;
- quantity assimilation and integration distinction as a level of understanding another culture.

As educational discourse sets the matrix of verbal interaction among individuals with different enophone consciousness in cross-cultural communication, its efficiency hugely depends on triggering mental cognitive patterns of the native culture and value reference frame. It occurs when socializing and acculturating, and their congruence in communication. National and cultural identification in students serves as the condition, part and benchmark enriching an individual in cooperation with others as the reference system of communication. Deciding on teaching strategies in this respect is the key issue which might be solved due to the conceptual approach to teaching in modern educational system.

In this regard, we must choose a textbook / manual on cross-cultural communication course which helps achieve communication goals among soon-to-be graduates in foreign languages. Foreign languages departments aim at developing students' personalities meeting their needs coupled with abilities. This purpose demands upgrading syllabus, new didactic approaches and principles. As of today, it is impossible to form and develop intercultural *communication competence in students* without a *competence-based textbook / manual*. The skills obtained are crucial for successful interaction with a representative of another social and linguistic background, climbing up the career ladder considering globalization and mobility.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The *purpose* of this paper is to provide teaching strategies relevant for developing values of national and culture identification in students when studying “Introduction to the theory of cross-cultural communication”.

The *main objectives* are:

- suggesting a number of communicative-pragmatic strategies to influence the addressee which are used to achieve educational goals, since the didactic component of the textbook involves relying on them;
- improving intercultural communicative competence, taking into account the organization of training in the light of the cognitive opposition "friend or other", acquiring a cross-cultural reflexive way of interaction, and further focus on value attitudes and participants' dominance in the communication act;
- fostering creative abilities in students, seen in their own intellectual and information products through the studied material.

Literature review

When addressing the problem of writing a groundbreaking manual for a language university, the authors relied on studies which focus on different facets of a textbook for higher education system. In the works of S.G. Antonova (2002), L.M. Orbodoeva (2003), A.D. Afanasyeva (2009), L.G. Tyurina (2007), E.G. Sakharova (2008), E.G. Tareva methodological assumptions for general theoretic manual and its modeling principles are defined. Both integral and external structure of the manual along with informative value, intelligibility, i.e. methodology, determines its quality as a communication tool. Besides, as researchers of academic books publishing highlight (Sakharova, Kleetskaya, 2007), pedagogical part shapes the pattern of learning and teaching materials.

The preparation of educational and methodological manuals for universities has its own specific features. Among the studies we came across a monograph written by N.V. Popova (2011), which is devoted to the development of a model for an interdisciplinary textbook of FL. There are studies which attempt to develop new forms of electronic (computer) support for the foreign languages training course and Russian as a foreign language (see, for instance, the works of E.I. Begeneva 2009, 2010). The purpose of these publications is to ensure the achievement of a specific learning outcome, which determines certain requirements for the content and material presentation format. When forging educational ideas, we are talking, first of all, about new methodological approaches to the selection of educational content and the structure of training courses.

The question is, why publish an educational book if textbooks on *cross-cultural communication* were published in previous years, for example (Timasheva, 2004). The work of O.V. Timasheva is devoted to the theory of this discipline. Yet, at present, the question of the students' practical skills development and intercultural communication skills, and not just informing them about the cultural specifics of a particular country or about theoretical approaches to this discipline, remains urgent. In university, when teaching the intercultural communication course, the textbook of Grushevitskaya T.G., Popkov V.D., Sadokhin A.P. is actively used (Grushevitskaya, Popkov, Sadokhin, 2002). The textbook provides a systematic analysis of a range of issues and problems arising in intercultural communication. The book offers theoretical base of the discipline which is crucial in a practical way.

Over the past 15 years, the modern pedagogical community has invariably raised the question of science and practice striving to form in a future specialist through all subjects (including a foreign language) those qualities and skills that are relevant for a specialist. With this approach, the textbook is, following E.G. Tareva, "such a methodical implementation of the model in teaching foreign language communication, which is aimed at the formation of a certain professionally significant quality of a specialist, implements the content of training due to this goal and includes special methods and techniques aimed at achieving this goal. Speaking about the characteristics of such a manual, it should be emphasized that structurally and functionally, it should stick to the specified goal, correspond to it both in content and structural-compositional components, determining their 'colour'" (Tareva, 2007).

At present, it is obvious that globalization of the information, economic and humanitarian domains lead to the expansion and deepening intercultural communication sphere, involving participants in the pedagogical process in a wide network of mutual knowledge and interaction. There is a need for educational publications to be focused on the "personality development potential" in students (Ibid.). The work based on an educational publication on the discipline "Introduction to the theory of cross-cultural communication" must inevitably be interdisciplinary (with the ideas and methods of history, cultural studies, linguistics, linguodidactics) and consider key sociocultural factors.

Methodology

The manual "Osnovy mezhkulturnoy kommunikatsii. Gosudarstvennye i natsionalno-kulturnye simvol'y" (lit. "Basics of cross-cultural communication. National, ethnic and cultural symbols") written by a team of authors for higher education serves as the formidable example of the textbook which fully and systematically reflects this area of knowledge (Basics of cross-cultural communication, 2019). The book provides linguistic and cultural aspects on national and ethnic symbols of 18 countries (Russia, Poland, England, USA, Australia, New

Zealand, Canada, France, Belgium, Spain, Italy, Portugal, Germany, Austria, Switzerland, China, Korea, Japan) as well as the European Union symbols. The manual features brief information about the states, their coat of arms, anthems, flags, awards and cultural symbols.

The knowledge of both target-language and native countries, their symbols and specifics are essential to the worldview formation in a future professional who takes a role as a mediator between cultures and thus must respect their own and foreign system of values and beliefs. When teaching such disciplines as “Linguistics and Intercultural Communication”, “Linguistics and Regional Studies”, “Linguocultural Studies”, “Theory and Methods of Teaching Foreign Languages”, “Translation Studies”, “Public Relations”, “Advertising”, “Regional Studies”, there is an urgent need to show the correlation and interdependence of different countries and people on specific examples, their cultures. Cultural self-esteem and incentive to preserve their own cultural values are manifested, first of all, in the upbringing of a respectful attitude towards the country's symbols. Therefore, it is vital to focus on advancing practical and intercultural communication skills in students and show the value of their national and cultural identification.

So, the methodology of this research is based on:

- fundamental approaches to the modern education system: student-centered approach (I.A. Zimnyaya, S.L. Rubinstein, L.S. Vygotsky, I.L. Bim, E.G. Tareva), intercultural approach (G.V. Elizarova, N.D. Galskova, V.V. Safonova, S.G. Ter-Minasova, E.G. Tareva and others);
- issues on intercultural learning of foreign languages (E.G. Tareva, G.V. Elizarova, V.A. Konev, L.I. Korneeva, R.P. Milrud, E.I. Passov, A.P. Sadokhin, V.V. Safonova, S.G. Ter-Minasova and others), issues related to intercultural communication in the study of foreign language (V.G. Apalkov, T.M. Balykhina, N.D. Galskova, T.G. Grushevitskaya, T.G. Sadokhin, G.V. Elizarova, etc.);
- an interpretive-evaluative method in mastering the textbook, which provides development of one's own attitude on the basis of studying the factual material presented in the manual and independently obtained information;
- comparison associations of a general cultural and special nature.

The manual heavily relies on *instrumental pragmatic approach* when solving cross-cultural communication issues. The approach prompts students to identify how values and beliefs impact intercultural interaction and when individuals might face unusual or barely known cultural symbols, customs, to name just a few.

Results

The authors rely on the idea that symbols characterizing nations and people have a special place in cross-cultural communication. Their history, heritage, conceptual evolution, significance acceptance in and out of the countries allow us to consider these signs-symbols the most important value categories necessary for successful intercultural dialogue. National symbols form citizenship, personal attitude to national attributes as the key national value and a badge of honour for its people. The educational part of the manual with strong focus on national and cultural symbols involves tips for students to realize value-based meanings of intercultural communication in a democratic society through such relevant personal characteristics as patriotism, tolerance, civic engagement (Tareva, 2011; Zheltukhina et al., 2016).

The didactic part of the manual “Basics of cross-cultural communication. National, ethnic and cultural symbols” suggests relying of a range of communicative strategies to influence the addressee. Our empirical evidence shows that we can identify as educational strategies in forming national and cultural identity when teaching “Introduction to the theory of cross-cultural communication” such strategies as:

1. Assimilating information strategy (informative strategy);
2. Reflexive strategy of comparing two or more cultures;
3. Valorization strategy of a native and foreign culture.

Informative strategy

When teaching a theoretical subject, it is crucial to understand that the reader relies on “information of a preliminary, guiding and signaling nature to proceed onto the next level” (Wasiliew, 2009). It seems important to solve the *problem of legibility*, which, due to the font variation (the use of a larger font size and bold type), presupposes a clearly expressed visual differentiation of different functions elements, instant recognition of all components of the publication design (Ibid.). What makes the manual “Basics of cross-cultural communication” stand out is its “reader's signs” (according to U. Eco) that are present on almost every page, drawing the addressee's eye to the key points of reasoning on a specific issue.

The strategic teaching of the intercultural communication course involves providing conditions for efficient manual reading which features traditional markers of the author's presence: conceptual sections and paragraphs headings, semantic focus on headings with visual code (for example, graphic highlighting). *Assimilating information strategy or informative strategy* is traced in headings, rubrication system through the *taxonomic program composition* tactics (Dimova, 2005) associated with knowledge modeling process and didactic objectives implemented within being informed on principles of teaching material structuring. For instance, pp.

3-6 feature a section that reveals the manual structure as a tool for a reader to search for the relevant information (Basics of cross-cultural communication 2019).

The Contents section gives the outlook on the content-factual information of the manual through blocks (parts) in Roman numerals as determinants to the word part. Such preliminary information stems from the prospection category, a constructive technique used, according to I.R. Galperin, to inform the reader on what information is to follow and its sequence in the process of reading (Galperin, 2016). It seems that such focus serves as a kind of a prologue for reading and is characterized in terms of a higher “communicative dynamism” (Linguistics, 2000). Prospection allows the author to shape the reader’s knowledge and direct his attention to assimilating the message of the book and engage them before they proceed to the text.

Moreover, the tactics of taxonomic program composition reveals itself in paralinguistics features (fronts and size choice, brackets). Such means are used as V.D. Chernyak, N.L. Shubina put it “for the communicative comfort” (Modern academic book, 2006) fostering students’ engagement and interest.

Since the informative function is the key one in indirect communication, involving the manual allows to turn to the informative strategy aimed at a specific type of knowledge translation which we identify, following A.R. Gabidullina, as “normative knowledge” – a kind of a reference point – to introduce students to the academic subject of *cross-cultural communication*. The pragmatic goal the authors set for students is to decide on actions to achieve result, that is, they need guidelines (Gabidullina, 2009).

The authors offer a set of communication-oriented assignments defining the strategy of digging up for information aimed at generating personal attitude and understanding of native and foreign culture, linking general and specific associations, expanding mental outlook (Basics of cross-cultural communication, 2019):

Read the texts, complete the assignments in the target-language (p 12);

Comment on the correlation between Russian history and its national flags (p 18);

Present chronological flow in a table relying on the results obtained (p. 18);

Draft a summary “Introduction to Great Britain” (p. 46);

Dwell on Spain country profile including key events and facts which seem relevant to you (p. 144).

Educational activity relies on social values, students’ attitude to which is focused on a socially vital invariant considered in society as an imperative – a norm, law, rule of behaviour obligatory to everybody. There is a

direct correlation between such value as “education” with the terms of science, creativity, culture, and mediated with the concepts of “innovation”, “novelty”, “pioneer work” (Sinyachkin, 2011). Being a socio-cultural phenomenon, the written texts of the textbook embody the value constants of society as the highest benchmarks of behavior that arise both on knowledge and the individual's own life experience.

The national political symbols make the empirical body of the manual. Countries' flags, coat of arms, anthems are means by which a country – native speaker – shapes national identity as well as retransmits it abroad. The information on national precedent names that each state promotes as political symbols is the crucial point. It involves political figures, heroes which contributed to the good of the nation. In the toponymy of settlements in any country, one can find names of distinguished artists, sculptors, architects, writers, poets, composers, scientists.

We believe that such selection of the teaching material corresponds to the principles of intercultural learning with the manual as the guide to the sociocultural context. Informatively new material fuels interest in students to interact with foreign languages native speakers and enhances the charm of a target-language culture (Vikulova et al., 2018). Along with that, creating positive image of a particular country is extremely important and the authors focused on that in “Basics of cross-cultural communication. National, ethnic and cultural symbols”.

Reflexive strategy of comparing two or more cultures

Since cultural space functions within society and embraces social events, it can be regarded as sociocultural. Introducing the sociocultural component to foreign language teaching reflects both intersection and comparison of cultural and social aspects in different societies. It was comparison that helped the authors of the manual decide on the learning materials that correspond to goals, addresses' professional aspirations, communicative and cognitive interests in students as well as their skills level. The criteria for the course “Introduction to the theory of cross-cultural communication” materials are as follows (Orbodoeva, 2003):

- *authenticity* (nation-specific materials, rules of functioning in cultures);
- *marked means of foreign cultural concepts* (ethnic, individual, transcendental concepts as cultural units involving value component).
- *variety of semiotic codes* (different channels of presenting culture significant information – verbal, non-verbal means (pictures, illustrations, etc.)).

Recently, there have been presented new conditions for the competence-based approach in teaching foreign

language and culture practice. For example (Tareva, 2015):

- shaping and fostering skills crucial for a linguistic personality mastering a foreign language as a communication tool: communication mobility, autonomy, sociability, tolerance towards unusual way of communication behaviour, individual style of foreign language communication;
- a chance to evaluate traditional technologies in teaching a foreign language potential: through native and foreign culture (intercultural approach), when a student being at the intersection of native and foreign culture has a deeper understanding of something different and reassesses and reconsiders their own system of values and beliefs conceiving it from the intercultural communication partner's perception.

Intercultural educational field is a priority concern in up-to-date linguodidactics. It focuses on studying foreign languages in a dialogue of cultures to prepare students to participate to cross-culture communication through foreign language as a tool of interaction between representatives of two cultures. The relevance of teaching a language on an intercultural basis also determines the result of the learning process for the “Introduction to the theory of cross-cultural communication in higher education” course in higher education. The idea of intercultural foreign language education, characterized by its own set of strategies and tactics, is a breakthrough in the system of modernizing teaching communication techniques for a new linguistic personality type ready for potential or real conflictogenic communication due to the information geopolitical paradigm. Under such conditions, the content of the preparation process for intercultural communication acquires axiological characteristics, becomes spiritual and moral, emotional and value-based, self-creating, pragmatically charged (Tareva, 2019).

Speaking about the strategy of reflexive comparing of two or more cultures, we note that on the pages of the textbook “Basics of cross-cultural communication. National, ethnic and cultural symbols”, there are many examples of assignments that are value-based. These tasks make students think, compare, and engage in complex communication processes (Basics of cross-cultural communication, 2019):

Refer to the section “National symbols of Germany”, “National symbols of Switzerland”, “National symbols of Spain”. Compare, where the image of bear is used as a symbol and why? (p. 30);

Refer to the corresponding sections on the symbols of Russia and Poland and compare

the symbolism of the colors of national flags. What do they have in common? (p. 41);

Compare awards and decorations of Russia and the USA, find similarities and differences in their merits. Refer, for example, to rewarding Soviet pilots for non-stop flights in the 1930s and 1940s. XX century (p. 67);

Compare the coat of arms of New Zealand with the coat of arms of other English-speaking countries. Identify the similarities and differences and explain them (page 89);

Compare the lyrics of Great Britain, USA, Australia and New Zealand anthems. Do they express only a national idea or a general idea? (p. 95);

Refer to the relevant sections for Russian, French and Italian state symbols and compare the color symbols of the tricolors of Russia, France and Italy (p. 128);

Compare the highest awards of Russia and Italy, write a comparative summary (p. 166);

Compare the state awards in the field of science, art and literature in Russia and China (p. 236).

The examples above show that prospective readers' learning activity is dialogic which implicitly implies the communicative experience of students obtained in the process of socialization in previous courses, as well as considering the professional experience and expertise of colleagues who will work with the proposed theoretical material. The authors conduct a dialogue with the reader, taking into account the linguodidactic potential of the dialogue (Dialogue Linguistics, 2019). The use of linguistic and non-linguistic methods of influencing the addressee contributes to the idea of dialogue with the reader relying on specific dialogue markers such as interrogative and incentive sentences to increase engagement.

It seems evident that such assignments guide cross-cultural educational paradigm into a different direction: learning native and foreign cultures *equally* with their mutual intersection and integration. In this case, the teaching strategy is to “consider the omnipresent interaction of conceptual system in participants to the communication act – representatives of two linguistic societies. What makes the strategy groundbreaking is its focus on *equal* positions of two or more cultures in cross-cultural interaction. This parity interaction imposes the following training sequence: *acquaintance with the fact of another culture → transferring it to the native culture and comprehending its features, → reevaluation / comprehension of the native culture fact and, on this basis, understanding its national identity → assessing another culture trait from I-position → reassessment of a different culture fact → forming perception of a native culture fact from the native speaker standpoint*. The ultimate goal of the complex cognitive and cognitive activity is, firstly, to appropriate the phenomenon of another culture, which is repeatedly (at different levels of rethinking) passed through the student's native culture, and secondly, to comprehend (reevaluate) the native culture fact, which, until the moment of comparison, could not be perceived as peculiar” (Tareva, 2017).

Valorization of a native and foreign culture strategy

The substantive aspect of the authors' text is in its conceptual focus on shaping positive and adequate perception towards the manual. This explains the reason for choosing *the valorization strategy* as the key one when promoting cross-cultural approach in the manual. The strategy as axiological aspect of argumentation regarding value assessments of the manual as prominent and novel in methodological terms increases the communicative potential of the proposed textbook.

With turning to *valorization*, the authors of "Basics of cross-cultural communication" manual attribute the innovative work social and cultural significance, priming readers to the prospective and urging them to rely on the new book. The strategy is effective due to the axiological aspect of argumentation, value judgments. The authors strive primarily to emphasize the innovative features of the educational publication regarding several features that distinguish it favorably on the book market (Basics of cross-cultural communication, 2019):

The semiotic (sign) component should be considered the fundamental basis of intercultural communication, which includes both language, the most important and capacious sign system, and other various signs. Expressing the uniqueness of a particular ethnicity in a number of other nations, sign systems play at the same time the role of bridges and a kind of conductors through which intercultural communication is carried out (p. 7);

The educational aspect of the manual involves guiding students' understanding of democratic society values, such important personal qualities as patriotism, tolerance, and civic position. Knowledge of the countries' symbols of the studied languages and own country language and heritage helps to define their own worldview, contributes to the formation of a future professional (p. 8).

The reason for relying on the valorization strategy in the analyzed manual lies in the complex nature of the learning material and focus on self-study and out-of-the box studying, and the authors emphasize such approach (Ibid):

For the first time the didactic manual brings together linguistic and cultural aspects on different countries that are usually studied in parallel without cross references in Russian universities. The practicum involves native and foreign languages and heritage, West and East, thereby directing the study of material to a cross-cutting, global vision of international and intercultural processes corresponding to the current state of affairs in the world (p. 9);

The section "Recommended references" is multimedia-based and fundamentally expands the learning opportunities. It boosts the cognitive process of understanding the text considering explicit internal links and surfing Russian and foreign-languages websites. It is a stepping stone for self-study in the foreign language (p. 9).

Such approach is possible with active information technologies implementation which increases educational process efficiency as well as quality of training specialists that meet the requirements of the information society. In this case, the question of the actual use of such technologies in teaching based on specialized educational electronic resources that meet modern didactic and methodological requirements arises. It urges to turn to the *strategy of valorization* at the level of native and foreign culture which expands research opportunities when teaching the course “Introduction to the theory of cross-cultural communication” using new external media – portals and sites that supplement the main educational publication and stimulate students to add their own results of educational and research activities to the information field. This strategy is built on the cooperative (dialogue) approach other training materials (Vikulova et al., 2020).

It is vital to define the course key terms as it expands students’ thesaurus which is crucial for them as linguistic personalities and soon-to-be professionals. Specific key terms (reading units) are translated in the manual thus they can be used as hypertext links. This enables searching the recommended information source (on a specific site) for additional specific information. The polycode nature of this book, where semiotic codes are combined according to the principle of verbal-visual unity, is realized at a fundamentally new, attractive level, when one can “talk not only about visualization, but also about polysensory nature” of the resource (Kozlovskikh, 2008). The manual meets the *ergonomic requirements* (Ibid.) with user-friendly interface and navigation options. Positive experience associated with working with the manual relates to its smart structure where student may start with any section and pace of work. Here are some examples (Basics of cross-cultural communication, 2019):

Dwell on one of the Russian cultural symbols of global value relying on the information provided by UNESCO World Heritage Center on cultural and natural sites of the world on the website <https://ru.unesco.org/>. Why do you think these monuments are on the list? (p. 29);

Listen to the US national anthem and give a short summary in Russian. Translate a few stanzas from the hymn into Russian in poetic form. Compare your version of the translation with the one at <http://onrevolution.narod.ni/USanthem.html>. What are the key words in the anthem from your perspective? Does this anthem reflect the national and cultural specifics of the country? (p. 66);

Explain the etymology of the word “nemets” in the Russian language. Rely on electronic dictionaries at <http://www.gramota.ru>. What is the difference between “nemets” and “germanets”? (p. 108).

With principles of navigation and operating mastered on the example of the recommended electronic resources, students can use other educational resources without much effort and time. This contributes to developing functional information literacy and ability to self-study in information environment. Apart from this,

educational information resource shapes algorithmic and visual-figurative style of thinking in students and assumes adaptability of such a manual to the individual abilities of students complying their knowledge, skills and psychological characteristics. There are assignments to the main texts focused on the students' personal approach to the questions (Ibid.):

Draft a summary "Introduction to Russia". What information was new to you? What is your geographical image of Russia on the globe? (p. 14);

Listen to the national anthem of Poland. Explain its name. What ideals of the Polish people are glorified in the hymn? (p. 35);

Dwell on the most significant US holiday from your perspective (p. 60).

The authors see problem situations of cross-cultural communication as the basis for special educational cases (Tareva, Tarev, 2018). For example:

You are a group of interns working for a teen magazine. The editor-in-chief assigns you to write a report on the symbols of Canada. As a result of group work, you should submit materials written in accordance with the requirements of the genre: titles, photographs, appropriate style. Keep in mind that your target audience is teenagers (p. 217);

Do you know how civilians and military personnel should behave when raising the national flag and singing the national anthem? Have you ever seen it yourself or in the press, television, cases of protest or disdain for the flag and anthem of both your own and a foreign country? Give examples and share your attitude (p. 266).

The case-method as the integral part of the native or foreign culture valorization strategy provides chances to develop critical thinking and apply acquired knowledge to solve new problems related to the professional background, get ready to participate to the cross-cultural communication within the comparative analysis of native and foreign cultures bias- and stereotypes free.

Discussions

The strategic part of the manual promotes didactic communication, performs the organizing function and involves:

- dialogic mode of didactic approach to the subjects of learning;
- problem-based learning that encourages intellectual activity in students;

- cognitive assignments that focus on revising and reconsidering actual knowledge;
- accumulating knowledge when comparing, observing associations analysing, focusing on inference and searching facts and information on the Internet;
- consistent end-to-end system of learning with the algorithm that helps understand the subject through reading key texts and delivering individual projects.

In its entirety, the didactic space, constructed this way, acquires an associative, dialogical, polyphonic pattern. In this case, the instrumental-pragmatic approach is crucial as it aims at speculating on how values determine intercultural communication when there is a chance to come across unusual and unfamiliar cultural symbols and make attempts to understand their historical past and explain their cultural significance.

Conclusion

In the final analysis, the experience of writing and working with “Basics of cross-cultural communication. National, ethnic and cultural symbols” allows us to consider it a rather efficient tool to shape the system of values of the national and cultural identification in students’ when teaching “Introduction to the theory of cross-cultural communication” course relying on the following pedagogic strategies: informative, reflexive strategy of comparing two or more cultures, native and foreign culture valorization strategy. The strategies are applied in the conceptual framework to ensure successful cognitive and communicative activity in students in intercultural communication. The engagement in native and foreign cultures dialogue reflects value-based, identifying, and emotional significance of the symbols for an individual, colleagues and people.

This requires the student to express an evaluative attitude to overcoming ethnocentrism and, thereby, develop the skills and abilities of intercultural interaction. The instrumental-pragmatic approach correlates with the described strategies and techniques of a personal, communication-oriented approach to the didactic process, and is supported by the interpretive-evaluative method in mastering the material and the case-method as a way of influencing the student's personality. The results of using communicative-pragmatic strategies show that such trajectory in teaching cross-cultural communication increases the motivation in students to study this course.

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